

A Novel Proposal to Test One-Way Light Speed Anisotropy via Stellar Interferometry

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(Dated: September 11, 2025)

ABSTRACT: The constancy of the one-way speed of light, a foundational postulate of special relativity, has not yet been directly tested in a synchronization-independent manner, as highlighted in frameworks such as those of Reichenbach and Mansouri-Sexl. While round-trip experiments (e.g., Michelson–Morley, Kennedy–Thorndike) confirm Lorentz covariance, the one-way speed remains conventionally defined by Einstein’s synchronization procedure, leaving open the possibility of directional anisotropy. All previous experiments designed to test one-way light propagation can be categorized into two distinct groups: full-terrestrial and source-moving. However, neither approach deals with one-way propagation effects directly. The full-terrestrial method infers it from a closed path geometry measurements, while the source-moving method relies on clock synchronization. We propose a novel stellar interferometry with dual-track approach employing a short-baseline terrestrial telescope ($< 1m$) designed to detect variations in the one-way speed of light without requiring clock. By measuring fringe shifts (or visibility alteration) induced by Earth’s orbital motion, we aim to test: (1) the isotropy assumed by Einstein synchronization, and (2) the possibility of dynamical anisotropy (the preferred frame’s effect). Unlike the previous experiments, these observer-moving approaches directly probe the alterations in one-way propagation of light from distant stars, induced by motion of the Earth. They are sensitive not to absolute quantities but to relative variations induced by the Earth’s motion. This paper is a conceptual feasibility proposal without a final claim about special relativity as no data has been taken yet. A non-null result has no contradiction with previous observations but would indicate the existence of a preferred frame of reference. This finding would refine the physical interpretation of the speed of light by demonstrating that Lorentz covariance is a matter of convention rather than a reflection of fundamental symmetry. Consequently, while the mathematical formalism of special relativity remains entirely valid, its ontological interpretation would require revision. A null result would empirically validate the second postulate, elevating it from a conventional definition to a fundamental physical principle.

Keywords: one-way light speed, special relativity, Preferred frame, stellar interferometry, simultaneity

I. Introduction

The principle of the constancy of the speed of light is central to the structure of special relativity (SR) [1]. However, while numerous experimental confirmations exist for the invariance of the two-way (round-trip) speed of light—most notably the Michelson–Morley [2] and Kennedy–Thorndike experiments [3]—a direct, synchronization-independent test of the one-way speed remains elusive. As emphasized in theoretical analyses by Reichenbach [4] and further formalized in the Mansouri-Sexl test theory framework [5], the measurement of the one-way speed of light is inherently entangled with

conventions of clock synchronization, rendering it operationally conventional within SR. Einstein’s synchronization procedure [6] assumes isotropy of light speed by definition, embedding the assumption of equal propagation times in opposite directions. Consequently, traditional experimental verifications do not independently assess one-way isotropy but instead confirm Lorentz covariance through round-trip measurements. This has left open the intriguing theoretical possibility that while round-trip light speed remains constant, the one-way speed could exhibit directional dependence—an anisotropy concealed by synchronization conventions [7]. Recent discussions in the literature have revived interest in probing potential anisotropies in fundamental constants, including the speed of light, in relation to violations of Lorentz invariance and searches for preferred frames [8][9][10]. Modern experimental proposals, including

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optical resonator setups [11], space-based clocks [12], and astrophysical observations [13], have attempted to push the sensitivity of tests of Lorentz symmetry to unprecedented precision. Nevertheless, these approaches often involve assumptions about simultaneity or synchronization that indirectly mask one-way light speed anisotropies. While modern experiments, such as optical resonators [14] or fiber-based phase-conjugate interferometers [15] constrain Lorentz violation to high precision, they remain insensitive to one-way light speed anisotropy. Resonators measure round-trip propagation times, inherently averaging any directional dependence, while phase-conjugate setups [Wang et al., 2006] rely on bidirectional paths that mask anisotropy through symmetry. Even clock-based methods [Greaves et al., 2009], which claim to measure one-way speeds, presuppose Einstein synchronization, thereby embedding isotropy convention into their results. Crucially, none of these experiments isolate the one-way propagation of light without synchronization assumptions or bidirectional averaging. Investigating the isotropy of the one-way speed of light remains a subject of ongoing scientific inquiry in modern physics [16], [17], [18].

A distinct class of proposals seeks to overcome these historical limitations by employing novel interferometric designs within a purely terrestrial laboratory [17]. While these approaches are ingenious in their attempt to isolate a one-way measurement, a fundamental challenge arises from their closed optical geometry. In principle, any experiment where both the light source and the detector are co-moving within the same inertial frame (a full-terrestrial setup) may be inherently constrained in its ability to detect a uniform motion-induced anisotropy. The reason is that a constant velocity vector imparts a global, path-independent phase shift on the light wave. For any two interferometric paths that share common source and observation points within the apparatus, this phase shift is identical. Since an interferometer measures only the difference in phase between its arms, this common-mode shift cancels out in the differential measurement. Consequently, upon rotation of the apparatus, no net fringe shift attributable to a uniform motion through a putative preferred frame would be observed.

This theoretical limitation underscores the necessity of a design that breaks this symmetry. The method proposed in this paper achieves this by utilizing a distant astronomical source, effectively decoupling the source of the wavefront from the motion of the experimental apparatus. This creates a non-common-mode condition essential for a potentially detectable signal. In this work, we propose a novel experimental approach utilizing stellar interferometry with a short-baseline terrestrial telescope to directly test for anisotropy in the one-way speed of light without requiring local clock. By observing potential fringe shifts as Earth moves along its orbital trajectory, we aim to discern whether

a directional variation in the speed of starlight can be observed. Unlike previous round-trip experiments, our method focuses on the direct one-way propagation from distant astronomical sources to the detector, thereby circumventing synchronization assumptions. In Section II, we analyze how interference fringes in a Michelson stellar interferometer may shift due to light speed anisotropy, when the telescope is rotated about the line of sight. While rotating the entire telescope presents practical challenges in maintaining fringe stability, Section III, proposes a cost-effective alternative: a miniature rotatable interferometer positioned at the telescope's focal plane. However, potential errors arising from misalignment of this interferometer and decollimation of the telescope must be accounted for, as examined in Section IV. Here, we introduce a method for deriving the total misalignment error using a terrestrial light source prior to stellar interferometry observations. Section V, introduces an alternative observational approach based on the visibility of static fringes rather than the counting of dynamic fringes. This static method is significantly simpler and can be done as an alternative test. In Section VI, we examine possible sources of error in detail, and in Section VII, we interpret the implications of both null and non-null experimental outcomes. The experiment is short timescale and since stellar aberration is compensated already when the star is aligned along the line of sight, it does not influence the results. The predicted fringe shift magnitude follows the relation $(\frac{B}{\lambda})(\frac{v}{c})$ where B is the interferometer baseline, λ the wavelength of observed starlight, and v the Earth's relative velocity. For a baseline $B = 1m$ and $v \approx 30Km/s$, $\lambda = 500nm$, this yields an expected maximum rate of fringe shift of 200 fringes per radian—a new constraint on one-way anisotropy, assuming a detectable variation in the one-way speed of light. This shift (if any) is sufficiently large to be distinguishable from noise.

This paper is a conceptual experimental proposal and not a final claim about special relativity. A non-null detection would suggest the existence of a preferred frame, consistent with a modern view of Lorentz-ether theory [19], while a null result would empirically validate the second postulate, elevating it from a conventional definition to a fundamental physical principle. Thus, the proposed experiment offers a critical empirical test, addressing a longstanding foundational question in the theory of relativity. This paper is not intended as an engineering blueprint or a detailed design document. The primary aim is to demonstrate the feasibility of the idea and to highlight its potential significance. Although the core concept is theoretically sound, some proposed details may seem practically challenging; these are acknowledged as areas for future investigation.

II. Theory of the Experiment

Michelson Stellar Interferometry is a technique developed by Albert A. Michelson in the early 20th century to measure the angular diameters of stars with precision beyond the diffraction limit of a single telescope. This method is both historically significant and technically sophisticated, laying the groundwork for modern optical interferometry in astronomy. The interferometer consists of two small mirrors (or apertures) separated by a known baseline distance (typically a few meters) near the telescope's entrance pupil. Light from a distant star passes through both apertures and is combined to produce interference fringes at the focal plane. Since the starlight remains coherent over the short baseline, the resulting fringe pattern depends on the star's angular size. For an unresolved point source, high-contrast fringes are observed. However, as the baseline increases and begins to resolve the stellar disk, the fringe visibility (contrast) diminishes. When Michelson employed his stellar interferometer, the telescope was aligned directly with the star, the projection of the baseline along the line of sight was zero, ensuring equal optical path lengths from the star to each interferometer arm. This paper addresses the question of what would occur if a stellar interferometer were rotated around the line of sight.

The projection of the interferometer's baseline onto the line of sight remains constant throughout its rotation, resulting in no change to the optical path difference. Within the framework of special relativity, both the one-way speed of light and the frequency of starlight are isotropic for an observer in Earth's inertial frame of reference. Consequently, these quantities, along with the wavelength, are invariant under rotation of the apparatus. As the phase of the starlight is therefore not a function of the rotation angle, no shift is observed in the interference fringes.

The observation of a stable interference pattern necessitates that the frequencies of the two interfering beams are identical; this isotropic frequency is a prerequisite for maintaining a constant phase relationship. A difference in frequency would cause the phase difference to oscillate rapidly, resulting in a time-averaged blurring of the fringes rather than a stable pattern. This isotropy of frequency is not an assumption but an empirical condition for the observation itself. Consequently, while frequency is constrained to be isotropic by the existence of the pattern, the respective wavelengths and one-way speeds of light along the two paths remain unconstrained by this condition and could, in principle, both be anisotropic or both isotropic. The Mansouri-Sexl test theory presupposes the existence of a preferred reference frame Σ in which the speed of light is isotropic and equal to c . We consider a laboratory frame S moving with velocity \vec{v} relative to Σ . Within this framework, the one-way speed of light in frame S for a light signal propagating at an angle θ

relative to the velocity vector \vec{v} is given by the relation:

$$c_S(\theta) = \frac{c}{1 + \kappa \left(\frac{v}{c}\right) \cos \theta}$$

For the purpose of this analysis, we assume the observed star is at rest within the preferred frame Σ . This assumption is justified by noting that any shared velocity component between the star and the Earth frame in Σ , would constitute a common-mode effect, contributing only to an unobservable phase shift. The observable anisotropic signature depends solely on the Earth frame's velocity \vec{v} relative to the star's frame.

Defining the dimensionless anisotropy parameter β as the product:

$$\beta = \kappa \frac{v}{c}$$

the expression for the direction-dependent speed of light in the Earth frame simplifies to:

$$c(\theta) = \frac{c(0)}{1 + \beta \sin \theta}. \quad (1)$$

It is this functional dependence that the proposed interferometric experiment is designed to probe.

Employing this anisotropic speed of light model, the round-trip propagation time T_{2-w} for light to traverse a path of length L and return is given by:

$$T_{2-w} = \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \frac{1 + \beta \sin(\theta)}{c(0)} + \left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \frac{1 - \beta \sin(\theta)}{c(0)} = \frac{L}{c(0)} \quad (2)$$

The resulting round-trip time is isotropic, as it is independent of the orientation angle θ . Consequently, the derived two-way speed of light is also isotropic and equal to $c(0)$. Therefore, this model satisfies the condition of two-way light speed isotropy. It is important to note that in this formulation, $c(0)$ is not an invariant quantity but a parameter representing the light speed in a specific direction. This model describes a convention-dependent one-way anisotropy; the value of $c(0)$ itself is not directly measurable without an external synchronization convention for clocks.

Given a measured frequency f of starlight in the terrestrial frame, the corresponding wavelength $\lambda(\theta)$ must be calculated from the fundamental formula $\lambda(\theta) = c(\theta)/f(\theta)$ for the posited anisotropy in the speed of light. Observing a stable interference pattern (at each angle θ) indicates the frequency of the counter-propagating light beams are identical. Therefore, the frequency is isotropic and independent of path's direction. Note that the measurement of f needs only one clock which fundamentally works based on round-trip light speed. Consequently, the wavelength becomes a function of direction (parameterized by angle θ) and is expressed as:

$$\lambda(\theta) = \frac{c(\theta)}{f} = \frac{(c(0)/f)}{1 + \beta \sin(\theta)} = \frac{\lambda(0)}{1 + \beta \sin(\theta)} \quad (3)$$

$\lambda(0)$ is wavelength of the wavefront along the line of sight. This wavelength does not change under rotation of the interferometer. By rotating the stellar interferometer around the line of sight, the angle θ and the wavelengths of starlight vary. Consequently, the phase difference between two counter-propagating light beams traveling a length of L parallel to the baseline is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_1(\theta) &= 2\pi\left(\frac{L}{\lambda_1(\theta)}\right) = 2\pi\left(\frac{L}{\lambda(0)}\right)(1 - \beta \sin(\theta)) \\ \sigma_2(\theta) &= 2\pi\left(\frac{L}{\lambda_2(\theta)}\right) = 2\pi\left(\frac{L}{\lambda(0)}\right)(1 + \beta \sin(\theta)) \\ \sigma(\theta) &= \sigma_2(\theta) - \sigma_1(\theta) = 2\pi\left(\frac{2L}{\lambda(0)}\right)\beta \sin(\theta)\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

The theoretical derivation in Equations (4) assumes that the anisotropic one-way speed of light affects the optical path difference while the geometric properties of the interferometer and the laws of reflection and refraction remain invariant under rotation of the stellar interferometer. Defining the fringe number as $N(\theta) = \frac{\sigma(\theta)}{2\pi}$ and the baseline (the distance between the two mirrors) as $B = 2L$, we obtain:

$$N(\theta) = \beta\left(\frac{B}{\lambda(0)}\right) \sin(\theta)\quad (5)$$

The rate of fringe shift with respect to rotation is then given by:

$$\frac{dN(\theta)}{d\theta} = \beta\left(\frac{B}{\lambda(0)}\right) \cos(\theta)\quad (6)$$

As the anisotropy is induced only by the differential mode of motion, then we conclude that κv is the transverse component of the relative velocity between the star and Earth. A longitudinal component of the observer's velocity—parallel to the line of sight—produces no fringe shift because it imposes only a common-mode change on the interferometer. The velocity vector alters the one-way speed of light and the derived wavelength identically for both light paths, as their propagation directions are symmetric relative to the motion. Consequently, the optical path difference between the arms remains invariant, leaving the phase difference and fringe position unchanged. The interferometer is thus selectively sensitive to transverse motion, which creates a differential effect between the arms.

It is important to note that this experiment cannot measure the one-way speed of light; rather, it constitutes a comparison between two propagation paths. A non-null result (an observed $\beta \neq 0$) would directly imply $\kappa \neq 0$ in the Mansouri-Sexl formalism, indicating a specific synchronization convention and revealing a preferred frame. For a baseline of $B = 1\text{ m}$, Earth's orbital

velocity $\kappa v = 30\text{ km/s}$, $c(0) = 300000\text{ km/s}$ and with visible spectrum $\lambda(0) = 500\text{ nm}$, this yields a maximum fringe shift rate of approximately 200 fringes per radian according to equation (6). The estimated fringe shift rate of approximately 200 fringes per radian is presented to illustrate the conceptual sensitivity of the proposed apparatus; this preliminary value does not include an uncertainty margin. A detailed analysis of the signal-to-noise ratio and potential systematic errors will be addressed in the feasibility study section, following a more thorough establishment of the concept's viability. The expected fringe shift per radian is sufficiently large to be detectable experimentally. However, an intelligent experimental strategy and detail design engineering are required to overcome key challenges.

III. Rotary Adjustable Mini Stellar Interferometer

To test the anisotropy of the one-way speed of light, a stellar interferometer must be rotated while maintaining stable interference fringes. However, the Michelson stellar interferometer is typically too large for practical rotation. As an alternative, we propose using a compact, rotatable mini-interferometer positioned at the outlet of a Cassegrain telescope, eliminating the need to rotate the entire large telescope. This approach ensures mechanical stability and maintains fringe visibility during slow rotation.

FIG. 1. Diffraction patterns observed at the focal plane of a telescope: one under perfect collimation and the other under optical misalignment.

FIG.1 illustrates the formation of a diffraction pattern from starlight at the telescope's focal plane. For our initial interferometric analysis, we selected Vega as the target star due to its high brightness and a spatial coherence diameter of approximately 35 meters, making it well-suited for this experiment. If the starlight at the telescope aperture is spatially coherent, the resulting diffraction pattern will also exhibit coherence. Instead of employing two separate mirrors at the telescope aperture—as in a traditional Michelson stellar interferometer—interference can be achieved using

two diametrically opposed points in the diffraction pattern. This configuration requires a significantly more compact and lightweight interferometer, which is both cost-effective and mechanically stable, allowing for smooth rotation without excessive vibration. We present a conceptual design for this setup, though detailed engineering will be necessary based on available equipment and facilities.

The setup requires the installation of a finderscope, aligned parallel to the main telescope's optical axis. This configuration is essential as it facilitates the main telescope alignment without necessitating the removal of the interferometric apparatus for use of an eyepiece.

A schematic of the mini stellar interferometer's optical layout is presented in FIG. 2. Within the transmitted beam path, a collimating lens is first positioned to parallelize the diffracted wavefront before it enters the rotary miniature interferometer. A band-pass optical filter is then employed to enhance temporal coherence and improve interference fringe visibility. For the superposition of two diametrically opposed points from the diffraction pattern, a Fresnel biprism is an excellent choice due to its inherent simplicity, lightweight construction, and mechanical stability.

The biprism should be mounted on a manual, fine-adjustment, single-axis micro-stage. This micro-stage is itself mounted on a hollow manual rotation stage, which typically provides both coarse and fine angular adjustment. The coarse adjustment capability is critical for reducing experimental time, as the fine adjustment operates at a very low speed. The lateral adjustability of the biprism assembly is used to modulate the optical path difference to achieve optimal coherence.

Following the biprism, a scientific CMOS compact camera (sCMOS) with manual focus captures the time-series of interference patterns, streaming the data to a computational unit for real-time monitoring, processing, and archiving. To mitigate distortions induced by vibrational or atmospheric noise, advanced computational processing is essential. We propose the implementation of AI-based algorithms designed to perform statistical analysis on the high-frame-rate video sequence. Unlike single-image enhancement techniques, this approach is designed to identify and reconstruct the underlying, stable fringe pattern by extracting it from the fluctuating noise across numerous frames. While no dedicated AI-based software exists for this purpose, the core algorithms are available and can be implemented in a programming environment such as Python.

All optical components are mounted on a single, hollow platform that replaces the eyepiece adapter at the telescope's output port. The entire assembly remains fixed relative to the telescope, with only the biprism undergoing controlled rotation or linear translation via its adjustable stages. This configuration enables the

software to simultaneously resolve the sidereal fringe shift and the precise rotation angle of the biprism.

The interference fringes align nearly parallel to the biprism axis. Under anisotropic light propagation conditions, biprism rotation induces a fringe shift perpendicular to the axis. As described by Equation (6), at $\theta = 90^\circ$ the fringes remain stationary while demonstrating a maximum phase difference between diametrically opposed beams. This corresponds to an optical path difference of about 200λ , which may lead to significant temporal decoherence effects. To preserve beam coherence at $\theta = 90^\circ$, an optical filter with a coherence length of L_c should be used which satisfies the condition:

$$L_c = \frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta\lambda} > 200\lambda \Rightarrow \Delta\lambda < \frac{\lambda}{200} = 2.5 \text{ nm} \quad (7)$$

FIG. 2. A basic design for layout of the mini stellar interferometer: 1-cassegrain telescope, 2-hollow platform, 3-collimator lens, 4-rotary stage, 5-linear stage, 6-optical filter, 7-fresnel biprism, 8-stand, 9-sCMOS camera

Consequently, observation of visible fringes at $\theta = 90^\circ$ requires implementation of a narrow optical band-pass filter. However, this configuration substantially reduces light intensity, resulting in severely attenuated fringe visibility. To overcome this limitation, we propose instead reducing L_c to 100λ and analyzing fringes at $\theta = 0^\circ$, where the phase difference becomes null. While this approach obviates the need for narrow band filtration, it inherently compromises coherence at $\theta = 90^\circ$, leading to complete loss of fringe visibility at this orientation. A band-pass optical filter positioned before the biprism

ensures that only light within the desired wavelength range illuminates the biprism, maintaining interference pattern contrast.

Stellar aberration does not affect the experimental measurements because the telescope is pre-tilted to compensate for aberration when the star is aligned along the line of sight. Consequently, the projection of the baseline on the line of sight remains null during rotation cancels out all stellar aberration effects. Although maximum fringe visibility occurs at an angle of $\theta = 0$, locating this angle precisely is experimentally challenging. To circumvent this difficulty, an arbitrary phase offset θ_0 can be introduced. The parameters θ_0 and β can then be determined simultaneously using the following procedure. The rotary stage is manually adjusted to four or five coarse positions, separated by intervals of approximately 3° , each yielding an observable interference pattern. For each angular position θ_i , the angular increment $\Delta\theta_i$ required to induce a shift of one complete fringe is measured. This measurement provides the fringe shift rate, $1/\Delta\theta_i$, at each point. Based on Eq. (6), the relationship between this measured rate and the angle is given by:

$$\frac{1}{\Delta\theta_i} = \beta \left(\frac{B}{\lambda(0)} \right) \cos(\theta_i + \theta_0) \quad (8)$$

The values of β and θ_0 can be extrapolated by fitting the data from all measured points to this equation.

IV. Misalignment Error Subtraction

When performing interference experiments with a stationary terrestrial light source—relative to which the interferometer has zero velocity—no light propagation anisotropy is expected. Consequently, the fringe pattern should remain invariant under rotation. Any observed fringe shift under these conditions must therefore arise from component misalignment and the consequent path length variation. Each component except the biprism may exhibit a misalignment, $\Delta r_i \angle \varphi_i$ (a vector quantity with magnitude and phase), which can be modeled as a dipole. The biprism is an exception in this setup because its lateral displacement does not result a fringe shift due to rotation. The vector sum of all individual misalignments yields an effective misalignment dipole, $\Delta r \angle \varphi$. This effective dipole represents a net optical path difference, which generates the observed fringe shift upon rotation. From this measured shift, an equivalent velocity can be derived using Equation (6); this quantity is designated the misalignment velocity vector.

After the misalignment velocity vector is determined through measurements with a terrestrial light source, the interferometer is realigned toward a stellar target and the resultant fringe shift is recorded. It is important to note that this realignment requires adjusting the focus of the main telescope to accommodate the transition from

a finite terrestrial distance to an astronomical source at infinity. Critically, this change of focus—a common-mode shift in the optical path length—has no effect on the average differential fringe shift measured by the mini-interferometer. This is because the interferometer is sensitive only to the path difference between its two arms, not to absolute path lengths common to both.

Applying Equation (6) to the stellar observation yields a total velocity vector. The net velocity component attributable solely to light propagation anisotropy is then obtained by the vector subtraction of the pre-characterized misalignment velocity from this measured total velocity.

In the absence of light propagation anisotropy, the fringe shift observed for both terrestrial and stellar light sources should be identical, as any shift would be attributable solely to instrumental misalignment effects. This misalignment constitutes a static systematic error that can be minimized through precision assembly but cannot, in practice, be reduced to zero.

To apply a misalignment error subtraction in the proposed experiment, a velocity vector must be derived from the fringe shift of each light source. However, this process is confounded by the presence of dynamic errors. Unlike static errors, dynamic errors do not produce a stable, measurable average fringe shift; instead, they introduce noise and render the interference pattern unstable. Specifically, dynamic errors cause rapid vibrations of the interference fringes, which are difficult to resolve by visual observation.

Therefore, mitigating dynamic errors is a prerequisite for accurate measurement. The dominant fundamental sources of dynamic error are atmospheric turbulence and mechanical vibrations, each of which affects the interference pattern differently. Mechanical vibrations periodically displace the pattern with a time-averaged shift of zero. Atmospheric turbulence, in contrast, primarily distorts and disrupts the coherence of the pattern rather than displacing it.

To overcome these challenges, the use of a high-speed, high-quality camera for pattern acquisition coupled with AI-based real time image processing for pattern reconstruction is vital. Without these technologies, conducting the proposed experiment with counting the dynamic fringes, while theoretically feasible, is not practically viable. Fortunately, there is an alternative simple approach with no need to count the dynamic fringes.

V. An Alternative Simpler Approach

Theoretically, the velocity of Earth relative to a frame in which the one-way speed of light is isotropic can be determined using a rotating interferometer, as discussed in prior sections. However, implementing such an experiment poses significant challenges due to its extreme sensitivity and the requirement for specialized

expertise. A key limitation stems from the need to measure fringe shifts during the interferometer rotation, a process that introduces instability in the fringe pattern.

In this section, we propose an alternative method for investigating light propagation anisotropy that does not rely on dynamic fringe shift measurements during rotation. Instead, we employ a fringe visibility test, wherein visibility is assessed at different rotational angles while maintaining the interferometer in a stationary position.

In an interferometric setup, fringe shifts arise from variations in the optical path difference (OPD) between the two interfering beams. The magnitude of these shifts is fundamentally constrained by the coherence length of the light source. Excessive OPD variations can degrade fringe visibility, thereby complicating precise measurements. By analyzing visibility under static conditions, we mitigate the instability introduced by dynamic rotation while still probing potential anisotropy effects. To investigate anisotropy in light propagation, the initial step involves minimizing misalignment Δr such that it remains below 100λ , half of the expected OPD due to light propagation anisotropy. An optical filter with a coherence length L_c satisfying the following condition is then applied:

$$\Delta r < 100\lambda < L_c < 200\lambda \quad (9)$$

When using a terrestrial light source, interference visibility remains unaffected by interferometer rotation because misalignment cannot render the two beams incoherent. In this scenario, as per Eq. (9), the coherence length exceeds the optical path difference. Conversely, when employing a stellar light source, anisotropic light propagation could induce an OPD of up to 200λ , exceeding the coherence length and causing a loss of coherence between the beams. Consequently, we anticipate that the visibility of stellar interference patterns will vary with interferometer rotation if light propagation is anisotropic. If, however, light propagation is isotropic in Earth's reference frame, no such variation in visibility will occur.

In Equation (5), the term $\beta B \sin(\theta)$ represents the optical path difference responsible for the shift in the interference fringes. The orientation $\theta = 0$ is critical, as it yields the maximum fringe shift and consequently the maximum fringe visibility. The degree of coherence remains constant for small angles but begins to decrease significantly once the path difference approaches the coherence length, vanishing at the coherence angle $\theta = \theta_c$. This angle is therefore defined by the equation:

$$\theta_c = \arcsin\left(\frac{L_c}{\beta B}\right). \quad (10)$$

To provide a numerical estimate, consider a baseline of $B = 1$ m, the Earth's orbital velocity $\kappa v = 30$ km/s, the vacuum speed of light $c = 3 \times 10^5$ km/s, a central

wavelength of $\lambda = 500$ nm, and an optical filter that imposes a coherence length of $L_c = 100\lambda = 50 \mu\text{m}$. For these parameters, equation (10) yields a coherence angle of $\theta_c = 30^\circ$. Although this calculation is approximate, it demonstrates that an experimental test for anisotropy via measurements of fringe visibility is both feasible and practical.

This method offers practical advantages over fringe shift measurements, as it involves stabilizing the interferometer at specific angles and capturing static interference patterns. This version of test does not need any fine adjustment in rotary stage and the coarse tracking is enough. By comparing visibility across different rotational positions, anisotropy effects can be discerned. Although this approach does not directly measure Earth's velocity, it provides a robust test for anisotropy of light propagation.

This alternative test, while simpler, is best conducted under calm atmospheric conditions. Although atmospheric turbulence may induce blurring in the fringe pattern, it does not preclude the measurement of time-averaged fringe contrast. The proposed method is operationally analogous to classical Michelson stellar interferometry: in both cases, the experimental procedure involves adjusting the coherence condition (here by rotation, in Michelson's case by varying the baseline), allowing the interference pattern to stabilize, and subsequently measuring the fringe visibility. If Michelson could reliably measure fringe visibility to determine stellar diameters through the atmosphere in 1920, then with modern technology (high-speed CMOS cameras, automated tracking, image stacking software, and better filters), we should certainly be able to measure visibility to perform this anisotropy test. Given its significantly reduced complexity and cost, we strongly recommend implementing this preliminary static visibility test prior to attempting the more sensitive and technically challenging dynamic fringe-shift measurements.

VI. Feasibility Study and Error Margins

A successful measurement of one-way light speed anisotropy requires a meticulous assessment of potential systematic errors and statistical noise. The predicted signal is a fringe shift on the order of 10^2 fringes/radian, which, while macroscopically large, must be distinguished from spurious shifts induced by experimental imperfections. This section details the primary sources of error and proposes strategies for their quantification and mitigation, including order-of-magnitude estimates of their size.

A. Systematic Errors

Systematic errors pose the greatest threat to the experiment's validity, as they can mimic the signature of

a positive result.

1. **Residual Misalignment Error:** Although the terrestrial calibration procedure described in Section IV is designed to subtract the dominant misalignment error, its efficacy depends on the stability and accuracy of the calibration itself.

- **Source:** Any drift in the interferometer’s alignment between the terrestrial calibration measurement and the stellar observation run will result in an unsubtracted error. Thermal expansion, mechanical creep, or minute vibrations could cause this drift.
- **Mitigation:** The calibration must be performed immediately before and after each stellar observation sequence. A linear drift model can be applied if a measurable change is observed between pre- and post-calibration. The entire apparatus must be housed in a thermally stable environment, and components should be constructed from materials with low coefficients of thermal expansion.
- **Estimated Magnitude:** The stability of the calibration is an engineering challenge. However, the requirement is that the residual misalignment error after subtraction is small compared to the signal. For a baseline $B = 1$ m and $\lambda = 500$ nm, a single fringe shift corresponds to an optical path difference (OPD) change of $\lambda = 500$ nm. A high-precision optical mount and a stable environment should aim to keep drift below ~ 10 nm between calibrations. This corresponds to a residual error of ~ 0.2 fringes, or a velocity error of ~ 30 m/s, which is negligible compared to the target signal of $v = 30$ km/s (~ 200 fringes/radian).

2. **Atmospheric Turbulence and Refractive Index Variations:** The Earth’s atmosphere introduces a time-varying refractive index that can distort wavefronts and cause fringe vibration (no shift). This is likely the most significant and challenging noise source.

- **Source:** Turbulent cells act as moving lenses, altering the optical path difference (OPD) between the two interfering beams on timescales of milliseconds. This presents as random fringe jitter and low-frequency drift.
- **Estimated Magnitude:** The coherence length (r_0 , or “Fried parameter”)[20] characterizes the atmospheric wavefront error. Under poor seeing conditions of 2 arcseconds, r_0 can be as small as 10 cm at 500 nm. Under excellent conditions at a good observatory site, r_0 can be 20-30

cm. The wavefront error over a baseline B is approximately $\sim \lambda(B/r_0)^{5/6}$ [20]. For $B = 1$ m and $r_0 = 0.2$ m, this yields a wavefront error of $\sim 500\text{nm} \times (5)^{5/6} \approx 500\text{nm} \times 3.8 \approx 1.9\mu\text{m}$. This corresponds to ~ 4 fringes of jitter. This jitter occurs at frequencies of 10-100 Hz.

- **Mitigation:** This is a fundamental challenge for ground-based interferometry. Its effects can be reduced through:
 - (a) **Short Exposure Times:** Using a high-speed camera (> 100 fps) to freeze the atmospheric motion. The differential measurement between successive frames can reject low-frequency drift.
 - (b) **Differential Measurement:** The proposed signal is a fringe shift *upon rotation*. By analyzing the differential shift between two rotational positions, common-mode atmospheric OPD effects over short timescales can be partially reduced.
 - (c) **Statistical Averaging:** Recording a long time-series of fringe positions at each rotational angle and applying Bayesian or wavelet analysis to filter out high-frequency jitter. Averaging over N independent samples reduces the noise by \sqrt{N} . To reduce 4 fringes of jitter to 0.2 fringes requires averaging over $(4/0.2)^2 = 400$ samples. At 100 Hz, this requires a ~ 4 -second integration per rotational angle.
 - (d) **Site Selection:** Conducting the experiment at an observatory with excellent and stable seeing conditions is paramount.

3. **Mechanical Stability and Rotation-Induced Artifacts:** The act of rotating the biprism must not introduce its own OPD changes.

- **Source:** Non-concentric rotation (wobble) of the biprism mount will cause lateral shifts and tilts of the optical component, leading to large, systematic OPD changes that directly mimic the predicted signal.
- **Mitigation:** The motorized rotation stage must be of high precision, with minimal runout ($< 1\mu\text{m}$). The effect of any residual wobble can be characterized during terrestrial calibration by measuring the fringe shift as a function of rotation angle *with the terrestrial source*. This measured error function can then be subtracted from the stellar data.
- **Estimated Magnitude:** A high-quality rotation stage can have a wobble (radial runout) of $< 1\mu\text{m}$. If this wobble translates

directly into an OPD change, it would cause a shift of ~ 2 fringes. This is a large systematic error, underscoring the critical importance of the terrestrial calibration step to measure and subtract this effect.

4. Optical Aberrations and Chromatic Effects:

Imperfections in the telescope and interferometer optics can cause path length differences that vary with field angle and wavelength.

- **Source:** The interferometer samples two diametrically opposite points in the diffraction pattern. Any asymmetry in the telescope's optics (e.g., coma, astigmatism) will yield a different OPD for these two points. Furthermore, the biprism's behavior has a slight chromatic dependence.
- **Mitigation:** Using a narrowband filter (~ 5 nm) minimizes chromatic errors. The differential nature of the measurement (again, shift upon rotation) helps reject static optical aberrations. The terrestrial calibration procedure inherently characterizes the total static systematic error, including these effects.
- **Estimated Magnitude:** For a well-corrected telescope, static aberrations should be a small fraction of a wave, likely < 0.1 fringes. This error is subtracted during terrestrial calibration.

B. Statistical Uncertainties and Fundamental Limits

The ultimate sensitivity will be limited by stochastic processes.

1. **Photon Shot Noise:** The finite number of photons detected per unit time limits the precision in determining the centroid of a fringe.
 - **Estimation:** The uncertainty in phase measurement $\Delta\phi$ for an interferometer is given by $\Delta\phi \approx 1/(V\sqrt{N})$, where V is the fringe visibility and N is the number of detected photons.
 - **Estimated Magnitude:** Consider observing Vega ($V=0.03$) with a 1m telescope. The photon flux is roughly 4×10^9 photons/s/m². With a 5 nm bandpass filter at 500 nm, the flux is reduced by a factor of $\sim \frac{5\text{nm}}{300\text{nm}} \approx 0.017$, yielding $\sim 2 \times 10^8$ photons/s. With a 50% total system efficiency, we detect $N_{\text{det}} \approx 10^8$ photons/s. For a 7-minute (420 s) integration per angle, $N_{\text{tot}} \approx 4.2 \times 10^{10}$ photons. Assuming a visibility of $V =$

0.5, the shot-noise limited phase uncertainty is $\Delta\phi \approx 1/(0.5 \times \sqrt{4.2 \times 10^{10}}) \approx 2.5 \times 10^{-6}$ radians. This corresponds to a fringe fraction uncertainty of $\Delta N = \Delta\phi/2\pi \approx 4 \times 10^{-7}$ fringes. This is **negligible** compared to other errors, confirming that the experiment is not photon-starved.

- **Mitigation:** This necessitates bright stars (e.g., Vega) and high quantum efficiency detectors. Long integration times at each rotational angle increase N and reduce the statistical uncertainty.

2. **Detector Read Noise and Dark Current:** The camera's electronic noise contributes uncertainty to each pixel's measurement.

- **Mitigation:** Cooling the CMOS sensor to reduce dark current and using a camera with low read noise (< 1 e-) is essential. Given the enormous photon flux calculated above, read noise and dark current will be completely negligible compared to shot noise.

3. **Fundamental Limit: Coherence Time of Starlight:** The finite coherence time τ_c of starlight, related to its bandwidth $\Delta\lambda$ by $\tau_c \approx \lambda^2/(c\Delta\lambda)$, sets a fundamental limit on the stability of the interference fringes.

- **Implication:** The fringe pattern undergoes stochastic phase fluctuations on timescales longer than τ_c . This is a noise source distinct from atmospheric turbulence.
- **Estimated Magnitude:** For a $\Delta\lambda = 5$ nm filter at $\lambda = 500$ nm, $\tau_c \approx \frac{(500 \times 10^{-9})^2}{(3 \times 10^8) \times (5 \times 10^{-9})} \approx 0.17$ ps. The corresponding coherence length is $c \times \tau_c \approx 50 \mu\text{m}$. This is much longer than the expected OPD changes, so it does not limit fringe visibility. The dominant noise source remains atmospheric turbulence, which operates on millisecond timescales.
- **Mitigation:** As proposed in Section V, using a narrowband filter increases τ_c , stabilizing the fringes and enabling longer effective integrations.

C. Conclusion on Feasibility

The predicted signal of ~ 200 fringes/radian is a strong effect. The primary challenge is not detecting a fringe shift, but *attributing it unequivocally to light-speed anisotropy rather than systematic errors*.

The quantitative analysis reveals that:

1. **Atmospheric turbulence** is the dominant fundamental noise source, introducing fringe jitter

of ~ 4 fringes in dynamic version of test that must be averaged down through ~ 4 -second integration.

2. **Systematic errors**, particularly from rotation stage wobble (~ 2 fringes), are significant for both versions but can be characterized and subtracted via the terrestrial calibration procedure. The stability of this subtraction is an engineering challenge but appears feasible.
3. **Photon shot noise** is negligible due to the brightness of the target star.

For dynamic version of test, the viability of the experiment hinges on the stability of the apparatus and the efficacy of the atmospheric turbulence mitigation and subtraction protocol. The required ~ 4 -second integration per angle is feasible. A null result will only be credible if the systematic errors can be demonstrated to be controlled to a level significantly below the predicted effect size.

For the alternative version of test (Section V), it is therefore imperative to directly compare the susceptibility of this method to that of the Michelson stellar interferometer, whose success demonstrates that the challenge is not insurmountable. The wavefront error σ_{atm} introduced by atmospheric turbulence scales with the interferometer baseline B and the Fried parameter r_0 approximately as $\sigma_{\text{atm}} \sim \lambda(B/r_0)^{5/6}$ [20]. Michelson's instrument, with a baseline of $B_M \approx 6\text{m}$, was profoundly affected by this noise source. Nevertheless, by relying on the integration time of the human eye to average high-frequency jitter and by identifying the *monotonic trend* in visibility as a function of baseline, he successfully extracted the stellar signal.

The proposed experiment possesses two decisive advantages that render it *less* vulnerable to atmospheric noise than Michelson's:

1. **Reduced Baseline:** With a baseline $B < 1\text{m}$ the wavefront error is reduced by a factor of $(B/B_M)^{5/6} \approx (1/6)^{5/6} \approx 0.2$ compared to Michelson's setup. The fundamental atmospheric disturbance is therefore several times smaller, resulting in intrinsically more stable and higher-contrast fringes.
2. **Modern Detection and Processing:** Unlike Michelson's qualitative visual assessment, the use of a high-quantum-efficiency sCMOS camera enables the precise, quantitative measurement of fringe visibility from a digitally integrated image. This allows for the collection of a large photon statistic over a prolonged static measurement at each angle, effectively averaging out residual high-frequency jitter and providing a robust mean visibility value.

Consequently, the dominant potential source of error is not high-frequency jitter but low-frequency

drift in the average seeing conditions over the duration of a full rotation. However, such drift is random and non-periodic. The simplified test detects a specific, systematic, sinusoidal variation in visibility with a period of 360° . A statistically significant correlation between measured visibility and the rotation angle would be unambiguous and cannot be produced by random atmospheric fluctuations.

Therefore, this static visibility test is not only feasible but is, in principle, more robust against noise than the historic measurement of stellar diameters. Achieving a maximum instrumental misalignment $\Delta r < 50\mu\text{m}$ and masking it by an optical filter $L_c > 100\mu\text{m}$ is practical. By definitively ruling out instrumental artifacts through a null result with a terrestrial source, any observed variation in visibility for a stellar source like Vega can be attributed to kinematic effects rather than experimental systematics.

VII. Analysis of the Possible Results

The proposed experiment can yield two distinct outcomes, each with significant but nuanced implications for our understanding of relativity.

A. Null Result (No Detectable Fringe Shift)

A null result, within the experimental sensitivity, would be a profound confirmation of standard physics.

- **Interpretation within SR:** It would demonstrate that the one-way speed of light is isotropic in the laboratory frame. This strongly supports the view that Einstein's synchronization convention, while a convention in principle, is consistent with an underlying physical reality where no anisotropy exists for a local observer in an inertial frame. There is no need to invoke a preferred frame to explain the experimental outcome.
- **Interpretation within Test Theories (e.g., Mansouri-Sexl):** A null result would place a new, direct upper limit on the anisotropy parameter. In the Mansouri-Sexl framework, the parameter β (often related to the β_{MS} parameter) would be constrained. The measured fringe shift rate $\frac{dN}{d\theta}$ is directly proportional to β . A null result at a sensitivity of $\delta(\frac{dN}{d\theta})$ fringes/radian would constrain the anisotropy parameter to:

$$|\beta| < \frac{\lambda}{B} \cdot \delta\left(\frac{dN}{d\theta}\right) \quad (11)$$

This represents a pure, synchronization-independent test of Lorentz symmetry.

- **Interpretation with Maxwell equations:** It would demonstrate that the isotropy of the one-way speed of light is an intrinsic property of electromagnetic radiation, independent of clock synchronization conventions.

A null result would reinforce the standard interpretation of Special Relativity, confirming that any convention for simultaneity yields the same empirical results for local physics, and that no preferred frame is detectable.

B. Positive Result (Statistically Significant Fringe Shift)

A confirmed, non-null fringe shift that correlates with the interferometer's angle would be a discovery, requiring careful interpretation.

- **Immediate Phenomenological Meaning:** The result would indicate a directional dependence in the wavelength of starlight as measured in the laboratory frame. According to the derivation in Section II, this is interpreted as an anisotropy in the one-way speed of light, parameterized by β .
- **Determining the Anisotropy Magnitude:** The experiment would directly measure the magnitude of the effect. The anisotropy parameter β would be determined from the maximum observed fringe shift rate:

$$\beta = \frac{\lambda}{B} \cdot \left. \frac{dN}{d\theta} \right|_{\max} \quad (12)$$

This is a direct experimental output, not an assumption.

- **Theoretical Implications:** A sinusoidal variation with a period of 2π would suggest the anisotropy is tied to the orientation of the apparatus in space. The most natural interpretation would be that the laboratory is moving with a velocity v (is the transverse component of the relative velocity between the star and Earth). Note that v is not velocity of Earth relative to a preferred frame. If the star and Earth are co-moving in a preferred frame with a velocity of u , then u acts as a common mode and therefore, is not observable.
- **Crucial Note on the star's Frame:** We assumed the observed star (Vega) is at rest within the preferred frame Σ and light propagation is isotropic in its frame. An inertial observer in Vega, using other celestial objects, may prove that light propagation is not isotropic on Vega. This would suggest that isotropy of light speed is not a universal property of inertial

frames. Consequently, light propagation within a given inertial frame could be either isotropic or anisotropic.

- **The Question of a Preferred Frame:** As light propagation within a given inertial frame could be either isotropic or anisotropic, an inertial frame with isotropic light propagation is absolutely isotropic, is the preferred frame. To use this experiment to find an absolute preferred frame (like the CMB frame), we would need to observe many stars in different directions and find the frame in which the measured anisotropy parameter β minimizes to a constant value (ideally zero). A positive result would be consistent with theories that incorporate a preferred frame, such as Lorentz Ether Theory (LET). In LET, the null result of Michelson-Morley-type experiments is explained by dynamical effects (length contraction, time dilation), while a one-way experiment could reveal the underlying frame. It is vital to note that such a result would **not** invalidate Special Relativity as a theory of measurement. The principle of relativity and Lorentz covariance would still hold for all experiments that, like Michelson-Morley, are based on closed paths. SR would remain an exceptionally accurate effective theory, but its interpretation would shift: the Einstein synchronization convention would be seen as hiding a physical anisotropy in the one-way speed of light, which is compensated for by the relativity of simultaneity.

In summary, a null result strengthens the standard foundation of Special Relativity, while a positive result would open a new window into fundamental physics, suggesting the existence of a preferred frame and demanding a re-interpretation of the relationship between convention and physics in the nature of simultaneity. A non-null result of this kind is a true physical effect that need not violate Lorentz covariance; it can instead be interpreted as revealing the physical consequence of employing a non-standard synchronization convention in a frame other than the preferred one. It would show that isotropy of light propagation in special theory of relativity is not a fundamental physical principle but is a matter of convention. The anisotropy is not an "illusion". It is a real, physical effect that is actively compensated for by the Einstein synchronization procedure. Furthermore, a non-null outcome could establish this experiment as a practical method for measuring the absolute velocities of celestial objects (by considering the CMB rest frame).

VIII. Conclusion

This paper has proposed a novel experimental framework to resolve a foundational question in

physics: is the one-way speed of light truly isotropic, or is its isotropy merely a convention of clock synchronization? We have developed a conceptual blueprint for a synchronization-independent test using stellar interferometry. This paper is not intended as an engineering blueprint or a detailed design document. The primary aim is to demonstrate the feasibility of the idea and to highlight its potential significance. Although the core concept is theoretically sound, some proposed details may seem practically challenging; these are acknowledged as areas for future investigation. The key achievements of this work are summarized as follows:

- **Theoretical Foundation (Section II):** We derived the central theoretical result: if the one-way speed of light is anisotropic, rotating a stellar interferometer around its line of sight will induce a fringe shift. The predicted shift is significant—approximately 200 fringes per radian for a 1-meter baseline—due to Earth’s orbital motion, making it a detectable macroscopic effect. Crucially, this model is consistent with the null results of all round-trip experiments like Michelson-Morley.
- **Experimental Design (Section III):** To overcome the practical challenge of rotating a large telescope, we designed a compact, rotatable mini-interferometer placed at the focal plane of a stationary telescope. This apparatus uses a biprism to interfere light from diametrically opposite points of the stellar diffraction pattern, making the setup mechanically stable and viable.
- **Error Mitigation Protocol (Section IV):** We identified that the dominant systematic error—fringe shifts from optical misalignment—can be precisely measured and subtracted. This is achieved by using a terrestrial light source (for which no anisotropy is expected) to calibrate the apparatus before stellar observations. The net stellar fringe shift is then attributed solely to light propagation anisotropy.
- **Alternative Method (Section V):** We proposed a complementary, static test based on fringe

visibility. Instead of measuring dynamic shifts, this method checks for a loss of coherence at specific rotation angles if anisotropy exists. This provides a simpler, cost-effective preliminary test before attempting the more sensitive dynamic measurement.

- **Feasibility Analysis (Section VI):** We conducted a detailed error analysis, concluding that the predicted signal is strong enough to be distinguishable from the primary noise sources, particularly atmospheric turbulence, which can be mitigated through high-speed imaging, statistical averaging, and a robust calibration routine. The experiment is not photon-limited for bright stars like Vega.
- **Interpretation Framework (Section VII):** We established the clear implications for both possible outcomes. A null result would empirically validate the isotropy of the one-way speed of light as a physical fact, not just a convention. A positive result would indicate the existence of a preferred frame while preserving Lorentz covariance as a matter of convention.

This work provides a road map for performing a definitive test of one-way light speed anisotropy. The author’s stance is intentionally non-committal regarding the expected result. However, it is noteworthy that the CMB dipole, which defines a local frame of rest relative to the cosmos, substantiates the theoretical possibility of a preferred frame. Consequently, this framework provides a viable context in which a non-null result—indicative of a one-way light speed anisotropy—could be detected. We recommend conducting the simple version (Section V) test before pursuing more sensitive and technically demanding fringe shift measurements. The historical success of Michelson’s technique demonstrates that such visibility-based interferometric experiments are feasible, even under terrestrial observing constraints. The implementation of this experiment now stands as a compelling challenge for the experimental physics community, with the potential to answer a foundational question that has persisted for over a century. This isn’t a high-risk gamble where only a positive result matters. Both outcomes provide a definitive, valuable answer to a specific question.

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